

DETERMINATION OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT OF CARDIOTOXIN BY DIFFUSION METHOD

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The molecular weight of cardiotoxin (an active principle isolated from cobra venom) has been determined from its rate of diffusion through a porous diaphragm (made of alundum) and is found to be approximately 46,200. The method and the principles of calculation have also been discussed.

Various methods such as osmotic pressure, depression of the freezing point, determination of the diffusion constant, etc. have been employed to determine the molecular weights of various substances. The diffusion method has been first successfully applied by Northrop and Anson (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1928, 12, 543). This method has also been used by many other workers to calculate molecular weights of various biologically active substances. One of the many advantages of this method is that it can be applied even to substances which cannot be obtained in the pure state. It is extremely simple in practice and readily available. It also facilitates the determination of molecular weights of proteins such as enzymes, viruses, etc. in a concentration too low to be measured by chemical methods but can readily be determined biologically. Further, to determine the diffusion constant, it is only necessary to estimate the percentage of the substance that diffuses out.

Though the method appears to be simple and advantageous, yet the calculation of the molecular weight involves many uncertainties and assumptions which, in practice, may not be valid. Firstly, it is not known how great an error is made in making the assumption that the particle is spherical and secondly, the molecular volume calculated from the diffusion coefficient will be high, because the radius given by the Einstein's law is the radius of the hydrated molecule. Since the application of Einstein's law involves various assumptions and numerous uncertainties, there is great doubt about the actual significance of the molecular weight obtained by diffusion method; in spite of these facts it has been widely used by others. It has been applied by Northrop and Anson (*loc. cit.*) to hemoglobin, by Northrop (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1929-30, 13, 739) to pepsin, by Scherp (*ibid.*, 1932-33, 16, 725) to trypsin, by Kunitz and Northrop (*ibid.*, 1934-35, 18, 433) to chymotrypsinogen and chymotrypsin, by McBain, Lawson and Barks (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1021) to egg-albumin. A thorough discussion of the method may be obtained in the papers of Anson and Northrop (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1936-37, 20, 575) and McBain and Liu (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 59).

In the light of the above discussion, it appears to us that this method will be most suitable for the determination of the molecular weight of 'cardiotoxin' for (i) it not a chemically pure substance, (ii) its concentration in the solvent

(after diffusion) is very low, and (iii) no chemical method is yet known which can estimate its concentration.

According to Einstein (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1903, 14, 235) the frictional force acting on a particle is equal to $kT/D\eta$ (k stands for Boltzmann's constant, T for absolute temperature, D for diffusion constant and η for coefficient of viscosity) and is a function depending upon the size and shape of the particle. If the particle is spherical then a measurement of diffusion constant will be a direct measure of the size of the particle, as it is related to the radius of the molecule by the equation,

$$D = \frac{RT}{N} \cdot \frac{1}{6\pi r \eta} \quad (r \text{ represents the radius of the particle}$$

including the water of hydration, and N , the Avogadro's number).

When r is known, the molecular weight can be obtained from the equation,

$$M = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 N \rho \quad (\rho \text{ represents the density of the substance}).$$

The simplest of the many methods to determine this constant is the one which deals with the measurement of the amount diffused across a membrane in a given period of time. One advantage of this method is that the concentration gradient can be maintained almost constant over a relatively long period of time. In using this method the membrane must be standardised first, since it is quite likely that out of the whole surface area of the membrane, only a small portion may be available for the purpose and also of the fact that the dimensions of the pores are not known. The membrane is calibrated by measuring the rate of diffusion of a substance, whose diffusion coefficient is known.

When a more dilute solution (c_2) is separated by means of a porous membrane from the other (c_1), then the quantity (Q) of the substance diffusing in a given time (t) is given by

$$Q = D \cdot A \cdot t \frac{c_1 - c_2}{L} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } D = \frac{L}{At} \frac{Q}{c_1 - c_2} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

(L represents the distance through which the solute diffuses). If the experimental condition is so arranged that the more dilute solution stands for the pure solvent, then the equation (2) is further simplified to

$$D = \frac{L}{A} \cdot \frac{Q}{tc_1} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Since the concentration is expressed as the quantity per unit volume, the same unit is also used to express the quantity that diffuses out across the membrane. If the time is expressed in days, and lengths in cm., then the equation (3) becomes

$$D = \frac{L \text{ cm.}}{A \text{ cm}^2} \cdot \frac{Q \text{ units}}{t_{\text{day}} \frac{Q_1 \text{ units}}{\text{cm}^3}} = \frac{LQ \text{ cm}^2}{At_{\text{day}} Q_1} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

(where Q_1 represents the number of units present in unit volume of the concentrated solution). If the quantity present per unit volume of the concentrated solution is taken as the unit, i.e., $Q = 1$, and the amount diffused is also expressed in this unit (i.e. as the number of c. c. of the concentrated solution containing the quantity diffused), then the above equation (4) is further simplified to

$$D = \frac{L \cdot Q_{c.c.} \text{ cm}^3}{A t_{day}} = K \cdot \frac{Q_{c.c.} \text{ cm}^3}{t_{day}} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

(where the ratio of L/A is called membrane constant and denoted by K ; $Q_{c.c.}$ is the number of c. c. of the concentrated solution containing the amount of the substance diffused in time t , expressed in days).

EXPERIMENTAL

The arrangement used for the measurement of the rate of diffusion and the cell are similar to those used by De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 308) excepting that the apparatus was placed in a refrigerator at 5° instead of the water-bath at 7° used by De.

Standardisation of the Membrane.—The ratio of the thickness of the membrane to its effective area is the membrane constant, K . It was calculated from the experimental results obtained by allowing standard solutions of NaCl (the diffusion coefficient of which is known) to diffuse through the membrane for a given period of time at a temperature of 5° . Then the membrane constant K was calculated from the equation $K = \frac{Dt_{day}}{Q_{c.c.}}$. Results appear in Table I.

TABLE I*

Determination of the membrane constant (K) at 5° .							
Time.	Vol. of NaCl diffused out.	Q per day (Average).	K_1 .	Time.	Vol. of NaCl diffused out.	Q per day (Average).	K_1 .
	2N-NaCl.				1N-NaCl.		
3 hrs.	0.58 c. c.			8 hrs.	0.56 c.c.		
6	1.15	4.36 c.c.	0.165	6	1.16	4.36 c.c.	
12	2.18			12	2.18		0.165

Determination of Diffusion Constant of Cardiotoxin.—Purified cardiotoxin, freed from salts by dialysis, was used for the determination of its diffusion coefficient. For this purpose a 2% and a 4% solution of cardiotoxin were diluted separately with an equal volume of Ringer of pH 7.4 to give the final concentrations of the solution to 1% and 2% respectively. The same solvent (30 c. c.) in which the cardiotoxin was dissolved and of the same hydrogen-ion concentration was placed in the beaker. The diffusion cell with its contents was then suspended in the beaker and the solute was allowed to diffuse for a definite length of time. The whole arrangement was placed inside another beaker of larger dimension, kept inside a refrigerator at 5° . The amount diffusing out in the time allowed for the purpose, was quantitatively removed and its cardiac activity was determined. From this, the total amount of

* Diffusion coefficient for 2N-NaCl and 1N-NaCl at 5° is 0.72 cm^2 per day extrapolated from Ohlm's data (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 70, 379).

cardiotoxin (in c. c.) diffused was then calculated. The density of cardiotoxin (mass per unit volume) was next determined by the displacement of xylene at 5°. Results are presented in Table II.

TABLE II
Diffusion coefficient of cardiotoxin at 5°.

Cardiotoxin = 1.0%				Cardiotoxin = 2.0%			
Time.	Amount diffused in c.c.	cm ³ /day (Q c. c.).	Average.	Time.	Amount diffused in c.c.	cm ³ /day (Q c. c.).	Average.
3 days	0.876	0.288	0.288	3 days.	0.583	0.291	0.288
2	0.554	0.277		2	0.548	0.274	
2	0.593	0.296		2	0.600	0.300	

The diffusion coefficient of cardiotoxin can therefore be calculated by substituting the values of K and $Q_{c.c.}$ in the equation (5)

$$D = \frac{K \cdot Q_{c.c.}}{t_{day}} = \frac{0.165 \times 0.288}{1.0} = 0.0475 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ per day.}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } D &= \frac{R T}{N} \cdot \frac{1}{6\pi r \eta} \\ &= \frac{1.83 \times 10^{-13}}{r} \frac{\text{erg. deg. mole. cm}^3}{\text{erg. deg. mole. cm. sec.}} \\ &= \frac{1.33 \times 10^{-13}}{r} \frac{\text{cm}^2}{\text{sec.}} \\ &= \frac{1.148 \times 10^{-8}}{r} \frac{\text{cm}^2}{\text{day}} \\ r &= \frac{1.148 \times 10^{-8}}{D} \\ &= \frac{1.148 \times 10^{-8}}{0.00475} \text{ cm.} = 2.41 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm.} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } M &= \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \rho N \quad (\rho = \text{sp. gr. of cardiotoxin g. cm}^3) \\ &= 25.4 \times 10^{23} \times 1.3 \times r^3 \\ &= 33.02 \times 10^{23} \times 13.995 \times 10^{-21} \\ &= 46,200 \text{ (approx.).} \end{aligned}$$

Thus the molecular weight of cardiotoxin comes to be approximately 46,200.

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